

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF SILDENAFIL CITRATE AS PHARMACEUTICAL RECONSTITUTABLE ORAL SUSPENSIONS ADVANCED DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS FOR MANAGEMENT OF PEDIATRIC PULMONARY ARTERIAL

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ABSTRACT

Sildenafil citrate, a phosphodiesterase type 5 inhibitor, is a vasodilator used in the management of pulmonary arterial hypertension in both adults and children. Pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH) in children requires precise, weight-based dosing. However the lack of suitable pediatric formulations often leads to unsafe practices like tablet splitting. This study aimed to develop a stable, palatable, and easily reconstitutable dry suspension of Sildenafil citrate tailored for pediatric use. Eleven formulations were prepared using wet granulation with xanthan gum, HPMC, and CMC as suspending agents, along with taste-masking excipients. Key results showed excellent stability (pH 3.3–3.6), rapid redispersibility. It was concluded that among the eleven formulations evaluated, F10 emerged as the most promising due to its rapid redispersibility, optimal drug dissolution within 5 minutes. F10 was the best formulation oral suspension as it showed a drug dissolution percentage 108% in 5 minutes was within the acceptable limit

as reconstitutable oral suspension of Sildenafil citrate formulations ADDS for management of pediatric pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH).

KEYWORDS: Sildenafil citrate, Formulation, Management of Pulmonary Arterial Hypertension, Pediatric Patients. ADDS.

INTRODUCTION

Background^[1-18]

Sildenafil citrate (SLC), a Phosphodiesterase type 5 inhibitor (PDE 5), is used in the management of pulmonary arterial hypertension (WHO Group 1) in both adults and children. It is available as tablets of 20mg, 25 mg, 50 mg and 100 mg strengths as well as an intravenous solution and oral suspension. The safety and efficacy of Sildenafil citrate for management of pediatric pulmonary arterial hypertension has been demonstrated, and the United States Food and Drugs Administration (FDA) recommends its use given continued routine monitoring. Sildenafil citrate is useful in management of persistent pulmonary hypertension of the newborn (PPHN), although use in children under one year of age is off-label. The dosing recommendation for SLC in management of acute pulmonary hypertension in children below 1 year is a starting dose of 0.25-0.5 mg/kg per oral every 4 to 8 hours, and 2.5mg three times a day for those aged above 1 year, with a body weight below 20 kg. Due to lack of a dose-specific formulation, current practice in resource limited settings involves splitting the adult tablets and extemporaneous preparations of liquid dosage forms.

Splitting tablets is based on the assumption that the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) is uniformly distributed throughout the product, which is often not the case. Tablets are often difficult to cut and divide appropriately. Their palatability is also reduced due to rough edges revealing the active drug's taste.

There is need therefore for a dosage form that provides accurate dosage, to enhance efficacy and safety, one that is easy to produce and dispense, with minimal manipulation to reduce the risk of errors. Liquid dosage form is highly convenient dosage form that takes into consideration swallowing difficulties especially among pediatrics, geriatrics, patients suffering from difficulties in swallowing, and repeated episodes of vomiting.

Sildenafil citrate has been demonstrated to be effective when administered orally in the management of pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH) in adults and children. It is particularly useful for the management of persistent pulmonary hypertension of the newborn (PPHN) although use in children under the age of 1 year is off-label. There however lacks a suitable dosage form for children locally, with current practice involving splitting adult tablets into multiple pieces to achieve doses fit for children, and the tedious preparation of liquid formulations extemporaneously.

Tablet Splitting is usually difficult and wasteful with the inherent risk of errors. There is need for a suitable and convenient pediatric dosage form. A 2.5 mg SLC dry suspension will be dose specific and highly convenient for children. The main objective of this study is to develop a stable, palatable, and accurately dosed dry suspension of sildenafil citrate for the treatment of pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH) in pediatric patients.

Sildenafil citrate has demonstrated significant benefits in improving exercise capacity, hemodynamic parameters and quality of life in children with PAH. Studies have shown that sildenafil reduces pulmonary vascular resistance and improves cardiac output, making it a cornerstone in therapy of pediatric PAH. Sildenafil is generally well-tolerated in children with common side effects being mild and manageable (e.g., headache, flushing, dyspepsia). Its safety profile has been well-documented in clinical trials and post-marketing surveillance. The selection of Sildenafil citrate as the focus of this study is based on several key factors, including its clinical efficacy, safety profile and the unmet need for pediatric formulations.

Formulation Development: To design a dry suspension formulation of Sildenafil citrate that can be easily reconstituted with water. To ensure the formulation is stable under recommended storage conditions (e.g., room temperature or refrigeration). **Stability Testing:** To evaluate the physical stability (e.g., sedimentation, redispersibility) and chemical stability (e.g., degradation of Sildenafil) of the suspension over a defined period. **Palatability and Acceptability:** To incorporate suitable flavoring agents and sweeteners to mask the bitter taste of Sildenafil, ensuring the formulation is acceptable to pediatric patients.

Dosing Accuracy: To ensure the formulation allows for precise, weight-based dosing, which is critical in pediatric PAH management.

Pharmaceutical Suspensions ADDS^[19-60]

Pharmaceutical suspension advanced drug delivery system is a coarse dispersion in which internal phase is dispersed uniformly throughout the external phase. The internal phase consisting of insoluble solid particles having a specific range of size which is maintained uniformly throughout the suspending vehicle with the help of single or combination of suspending agent. The external phase (suspending medium) is usually aqueous in some case, may be an organic or oily liquid for non-oral use.

The dispersed particle should not settle readily and the settle particles should redisperse suddenly, on settling cake should not form by the particle, preparation can be easily poured, it should be chemically and physically stable, it should be palatable and it should be free from gritting particle.

Advantages of Dry Granules for Oral Suspension

There is accurate single dosing as the dose is packed in single dose-sachets, drug dose is relatively independent of any physical factors like temperature, sedimentation rate and liquid flow properties, packaging of the powder mixture is done in sachets (single dose) making the formulation easy to carry, enhanced convenience of single dosage regimen, colored, flavored, sweetened formulation is advantageous for administration to the pediatric population and stable on storage and when reconstituted with an ingestible liquid for administration, the corresponding liquid suspension is stable for the duration for which the therapy is required.

Disadvantages of Liquid Oral Suspension

Liquid oral suspension has certain disadvantages, to overcome these disadvantages a reconstitutable suspension is prepared, there are chances of inaccuracy in single dosing because it is a bulk formulation, drug dose depends on various physical factors of the dosage form such as temperature of storage, sedimentation rate of the formulation, liquid flow properties like viscosity, pourability, redispersion, flocculation and content uniformity, the drug may be less stable in a liquid formulation rather than in tablets or capsules, stability of the liquid suspension largely depends on the temperature of storage and caking occurs upon storage.

A Reconstitutable Suspension

A reconstitutable pharmaceutical suspension is defined as a finely divided insoluble particle ranging from 0.5-5 μ , which is to be distributed in a suitable vehicle. A reconstitutable suspension is a solid dosage form that can be reconstituted by the addition of water to administer by the oral route. Mostly antibiotics, some moisture sensitive and pediatric drugs are available in the form of dry suspension. The reconstituted system is the formulation of choice when the drug stability is a major concern. The dry mix for oral suspension contains the drug, colorants, flavors, sweeteners, stabilizing agents, suspending agents and preserving agents that may be needed to enhance the stability of the formulation. A reconstitutable suspension form of drug shows improved bioavailability as compared to tablets and capsules as it is in the dispersed state at the time of administration. A reconstitutable suspension can

offer several advantages such as maintenance of the chemical stability of the active compounds until reconstitution at the start of treatment. The same suspension can be easily administered to children of different ages by adjusting the volume to swallow.

In the present study, it was proposed to formulate of Sildenafil citrate as reconstitutable oral suspension development formulations advanced drug delivery systems ADDS by using wet granulation technique method, for management of pediatric pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sildenafil and all raw materials used in the formulation including active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs), excipients, and analytical reagents were obtained as a gift sample from (Modern Pharmaceutical Industry Company-Yemen) and (Shaphaco Pharmaceutical Industry Company-Yemen). As shown in Table 1.

Table 1: List of Materials Used.

No	Materials
1	Sildenafil Citrate
2	Xanthan Gum
3	HPMC
4	CMC
5	Citric Acid
6	Sodium Benzoate
7	Strawberry Flavor
8	Mentha Piperita
9	Aspartame
10	Sucralose
11	Sucrose
12	Purified Water
13	Ethanol
14	Methanol

Equipment

Table 2: The equipment used.

the equipments used as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: The Equipment's Used.

No	Equipment's
1	UV/VIS Spectrophotometer
2	Viscometer
3	pH Meter

4	Electronic Balance
5	Viscometer
6	Dissolution Tester
7	Tap Density Tester

METHODS

Formulation and Evaluation of Drug^[61-145]

Solubility of Sildenafil Citrate

The pharmacopeial expression of solubility is the number of milliliters of solvent in which 1gram of solute will dissolve to make a saturated solution. solubility of sildenafil citrate was performed by gravimetric method at 25C° by using different solvent including water, methanol, ethanol, and buffer solution and the result compared to the values as shown in the Table 3.

Table 3: Solubility Specification of Drugs.

Descriptive Term	Parts of Solvent Required for 1Part of Solute:
Very Soluble	Less than 1
Freely Soluble	From 1 to 10
Soluble	From 10 to 30
Sparingly Soluble	From 30 to 100
Slightly Soluble	From 100 to 1000
Very Slightly Soluble	From 1000 to 10000
Practically Insoluble, or Insoluble	Greater than or equal to 10,000.

Preparation of Sildenafil Citrate Reconstitutable Suspension Formulations

Sildenafil citrate reconstitutable suspension prepared by wet granulation.

Preparation process: All ingredients required for preparation of reconstitute suspension were accurately weighed, then passed through mesh no.18 separately and then mix until get homogeneous powder, after that drops of Ethanol 98% was add gently to the powder and mix to make wet granules, then the granules drying on the oven for 30miutes at 50C° and finally, sieve the granules through mesh no. 25. As shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Composition of Sildenafil Citrate Suspension Formulations.

Ingredients	Formulation code (mg)										
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11
Sildenafil Citrate	0.351	0.351	0.351	0.351	0.351	0.351	0.351	0.351	0.351	0.351	0.351
Xanthan Gum	1	0.5	0.5	0.3	0.25	0.4	0.25	0.2	0.7	0.3	0.3
HPMC	0.5	0.7	0.5	0.5	0.5	---	---	---	---	---	---

CMC	---	---	---	---	---	0.3	0.5	0.6		---	---
Citric acid anhydrous	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Sodium Benzoate	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Strawberry Flavoring	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Mentha piperita	---	---	---	---	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Aspartame	---	1	---	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Sucralose	---	---	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Sucrose	22.199	21.499	22.199	21.399	21.349	21.499	21.499	21.399	21.499	21.899	21.899
Purified Water	up to 100ml										

The formulations F1-F5 used to development the formulations F6-F11. Then the formulations F6-F11 evaluated according to evaluation parameters for oral suspensions.

Micrometric Properties Evaluation of The Powder

Angle of Repose (θ)

Angle of repose is defined as the maximum angle possible between the surface of a pile of the powder and horizontal plane. The frictional force in a loose powder or granules can be measured by angle of repose as shown in Table 5.

$$\tan \theta = h/r$$

$\theta = \tan^{-1} (h/r)$ Where, θ is the angle of repose, h is the height of pile, r is the radius of the base of pile.

Table 5: Relationship Between Angle of Repose and Flow Properties.

Flow Property	Angle of Repose
Excellent	<25
Good	25-30
Passable	40-30
Very Poor	>40

Bulk Density

Bulk density is defined as the mass of a powder divided by the bulk volume. The bulk density of a powder depends primarily on particle size distribution, particle shape, and the tendency of the particles to adhere to one another.

$$\text{LBD} = \frac{\text{Weight of the powder (m)}}{\text{Volume of the packing (vo)}}$$

Tapped Density

The measuring cylinder containing a known mass of blend was tapped for a fixed time. The minimum volume (V_t) occupied in the cylinder and the weight (M) of the blend was measured. The tapped density (ρ_t) was calculated using the following formula.

$$\rho_t = M / V_t$$

Compressibility Index

The compressibility index of the granules was determined by Carr's compressibility index as shown in Table 6.

(%) Carr's Index can be calculated by using the following formula:

$$\text{Carr's Index (\%)} = \text{TBD} - \text{LBD} / \text{TBD} \times 100$$

Hausner Ratio

Hausner ratio is an indirect index of ease of powder flow. It is calculated by the following formula:

$$\text{Hausner ratio} = \rho_t / \rho_d$$

Where ρ_t is tapped density and ρ_d is bulk density. Lower Hausner ratio (<1.25) indicates better flow properties than higher ones (>1.25).

Table 6: Grading of the Powders for Their Flow Properties According to Carr's Index.

Compressibility Index	Flow Properties
5-15	Excellent
12-16	Good
18-21	Fair to Passable
23-35	Poor
33-38	Very Poor
>40	Very Very Poor

Evaluation of Suspension Stability

Techniques for evaluating suspension generally are complex and are far from being completely satisfactory. Some test methods are somewhat empiric in nature, i.e. the exact basis on which they operate cannot be explicitly defined mathematically. All test procedures suffer from some limitations, and the results, therefore, must be cautiously evaluated and interpreted.

Organoleptic Properties

Organoleptic aspects are important considerations in oral suspension. Variations or changes in color, taste and flavor indicate chemical as well as physical instability. Change in

organoleptic aspects could be attributed to the nonuniform distribution of ingredients, crystal growth and subsequent particle dissolution.

pH Parameter

The pH of the suspension must be between 3-4.5 for optimum stability. The pH of the suspension was measured with the aid of PH meter. The pH values were measured at $25 \pm 1\text{C}^\circ$ using a pH digital meter. The formulation was brought in contact with the electrode of pH meter and equilibrated for 1 min. This method was done in triplicate and mean was calculated along with standard deviation.

Viscosity Measurement

The viscosity of the samples was determined at 25C° by using viscometer (Brook Field), Model: DV2TRVTJO at 100 revolution/min (Spindle \neq 4). to ensure proper consistency for dosing.

Sedimentation Volume

Sedimentation volume (F) is a ratio of the final volume of sediment (V_u) to the original volume of sediment (V_o) before settling. 50ml of each suspension were transferred to 50 ml measuring cylinders and the volume of sediment formed was noted at every 24 hr for 7 days. The sedimentation volume F (%), was calculated using the formula.

$$F = 100 V_u / V_o$$

Redispersibility

Redispersibility of suspension is one of the major considerations in assessing the acceptability of a suspension. The sediment formed should be easily dispersed by moderate shaking to yield a homogeneous system, hence, measuring the sedimentation volume and its ease of redispersion are two of the most common basic evaluative procedures. The redispersibility is determined by studying the number of strokes to redisperse the formed sediment at the end of 7 days of storage of the formulations (not more than 100 strokes).

In-Vitro Dissolution

The in vitro dissolution studies were carried out using USP apparatus Type II at 100 rpm. The dissolution medium consisted of 900 ml 0.1N HCL maintained at $37\text{C}^\circ \pm 0.5\text{C}^\circ$. 5ml of the suspension was placed inside the vessel at time zero. Samples were withdrawn after time interval 5,10 and 15min. Maintaining sink condition, the taking solutions were further diluted

with 0.1N HCL and absorbance measured in UV spectrophotometer (UV 290nm). The results were calculated by using the formula.

$$\% \text{ Drug Release} = ((\text{concentration}(\text{mg}) * \text{volume}(\text{ml}) / \text{Total drug} (\text{mg}))) * 100$$

To determine unknown concentration of the sample

$$\text{Con.} = (\text{abs} + \text{intercept}) / \text{slope.}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Solubility of Sildenafil Citrate

Table 7: Solubility of Sildenafil Citrate in Different Solvents.

Medium	Part of Solute in mg	Part of Solvent in ml	Result
Ethanol 70%	100 mg	10 ml	Sparingly Soluble
Methanol 60%	100 mg	20 ml	Slightly Soluble
pH 0.1 HCL	100 mg	25 ml	Slightly Soluble
pH 4.5 Buffer	100 mg	35 ml	Slightly Soluble
pH 6.8 Buffer	100 mg	More than 1000 ml	Insoluble
Distal Water	100 mg	45 ml	Slightly Soluble

Drug Solubility

Sildenafil poor water solubility was mitigated by using ethanol in granulation and suspending agents to maintain uniformity. The formulations align with WHO guidelines for pediatric PAH, offering a safer alternative to tablet splitting. The use of xanthan gum (F6/F11) provided superior viscosity and stability, consistent with studies highlighting its pseudoplastic behavior and pH tolerance. The drug solubility in different media it found to be sparingly soluble to slightly soluble as shown in Table 7.

Micromeritic Properties of the Powder

Table 8: Micromeritic Properties of the Powder.

Formulation Code	Bulk Density g/mL	Tapped Density g/mL	Voids	Porosity%
F6	0.784	1.004	0.21	21%
F7	0.777	1.0244	0.24	24%
F8	0.806	0.961	0.16	16%
F9	0.728	0.9444	0.22	22%
F10	0.714	0.961	0.26	26%
F11	0.90	1.00	0.10	10%

Table 9: Micromeritic Properties of the Powder.

Formulation Code	Carr's Index	Hausner' Ratio	Angle of Repose	Flowability
F6	21.91	1.280	45	Possible
F7	24.150	1.318	45	Possible
F8	16	1.19	43	Possible
F9	22.914	1.297	42	Possible
F10	25.70	1.345	54	Poor
F11	12	1.11	29	Excellent

Micromeritic Properties

The angle of repose of formulations was found to be between 29 to 45 that means it's possible. The angle of repose while other formulations was found to be 29, which indicates excellent properties. The bulk density was found to be between 0.78 to 0.90 g/cm³. The tapped density was found to be between 0.94 to 1.02 g/cm³, the compressibility index was found to be in the range of 12 to 24.15% and the Hausner ratio lies between 1.11 to 1.34. The results in terms of micromeritics properties revealed that the flow property of formulations F11 were excellent and other formulations were possible as shown in Tables 8 and 9.

Evaluation of Suspension Stability

Organoleptic Properties

The organoleptic properties of Sildenafil as shown in Table 10.

Table 10: Characterization of the Powder.

Formulation Code	Color	Taste	Odor	Shape
F6	White	Sweet	Strawberry Flavor	Granules
F7	White	Sweet	Strawberry Flavor	Granules
F8	White	Sweet	Strawberry Flavor	Granules
F9	White	Sweet	Strawberry Flavor	Granules
F10	White	Sweet	Strawberry Flavor	Granules
F11	White	Sweet	Strawberry Flavor	Granules

The organoleptic properties like color, odor and taste of the API were evaluated. The color of Sildenafil was found to be a white powder, characteristic odor was found to be strawberry flavor and the taste sweet. As shown in Table 10.

pH Determination

The pH determination results of Sildenafil formulations as shown in Table 11.

Table 11: pH of Sildenafil Citrate Formulation Suspensions.

Formulation Code	First Day	After 5 Days	After 10 Days	After 15 Days
F6	3.48	3.47	3.47	3.45
F7	3.52	3.52	3.50	3.51
F8	3.39	3.37	3.38	3.37
F9	3.58	3.57	3.57	3.57
F10	3.55	3.54	3.52	3.53
F11	3.39	3.39	3.38	3.39

The results of pH determination of formulations were found to be maintained between pH 3.3–3.6 (optimal for Sildenafil stability) over 15 days.

Viscosity Measurement

The viscosity measurement results of Sildenafil formulations as shown in Table 12.

Table 12: Viscosity of Sildenafil Citrate Formulation Suspensions.

Formulation Code	First day	After 5 Days	After 10 Days	After 15 Days
F6	210	230	232	235
F7	845	890	895	895
F8	798	796	795	793
F9	454	564	570	572
F10	235	250	252	256
F11	230	252	255	260
Unit	Cp	Cp	Cp	Cp

The results of viscosity measurement of formulations were found to be F7 (845 cP) and F8 (798 cP) showed higher viscosity due to higher xanthan gum/HPMC content, which may enhance suspension stability but could affect pourability as shown in Table 12.

Redispersibility

The redispersibility of Sildenafil formulations as shown in Table 13.

Table 13: Redispersibility of Sildenafil Citrate Formulation Suspensions.

Formulation Code	At Time Zero	After 5 Days	After 10 Days	After 15 Days
F6	4	4	4	5
F7	7	8	8	8
F8	7	7	8	8
F9	5	5	5	5
F10	4	5	5	6
F11	4	4	5	5

All the formulations were redispersibility quickly to form homogeneous suspension. All formulations required ≤ 8 strokes (F6/F11: 4–5 strokes), meeting ideal suspension criteria. As shown in Table 13.

In-Vitro Dissolution

The drug dissolution results of Sildenafil formulations as shown in Tables (14-20).

Table 14: Absorbance of Sildenafil Citrate Suspension Formulation F6.

F6	Abs After 5 min	Abs After 10 min	Abs After 15 min
Abs 1	0.0743	0.0668	0.0674
Abs 2	0.0744	0.0669	0.0675
Abs 3	0.0745	0.0671	0.0675
Average Abs	0.2232	0.2008	0.2024

Table 15: Absorbance of Sildenafil Citrate Suspension Formulation F7.

F7	Abs After 5 min	Abs After 10 min	Abs After 15 min
Abs 1	0.0786	0.0787	0.0773
Abs 2	0.0787	0.0788	0.0774
Abs 3	0.0787	0.079	0.0776
Average Abs	0.236	0.2365	0.2323

Table 16: Absorbance of Sildenafil Citrate Suspension Formulation F8.

F8	Abs After 5 min	Abs After 10 min	Abs After 15 min
Abs 1	0.0834	0.083	0.0995
Abs 2	0.0835	0.0831	0.0996
Abs 3	0.0836	0.0833	0.0998
Average Abs	0.2505	0.2494	0.2989

Table 17: Absorbance of Sildenafil Citrate Suspension Formulation F9.

F9	Abs After 5 min	Abs After 10 min	Abs After 15 min
Abs 1	0.0861	0.1004	0.1013
Abs 2	0.0862	0.1005	0.1014
Abs 3	0.0864	0.1006	0.1015
Average Abs	0.2587	0.3015	0.3042

Table 18: Absorbance of Sildenafil Citrate Suspension Formulation F10.

F10	Abs After 5 min	Abs After 10 min	Abs After 15 min
Abs 1	0.0869	0.0986	0.0967
Abs 2	0.087	0.0987	0.0968
Abs 3	0.0872	0.0987	0.097
Average Abs	0.2611	0.296	0.2905

Table 19: Absorbance of Sildenafil Citrate Suspension Formulation F11.

F11	Abs After 5 min	Abs After 10 min	Abs After 15 min
Abs 1	0.0756	0.0879	0.0773
Abs 2	0.0757	0.088	0.0774
Abs 3	0.0759	0.0882	0.0776
Average Abs	0.2272	0.2641	0.2323

Table 18: Absorbance of Sildenafil Citrate Suspension Formulations.

Formulation Code	Abs After 5 min	Abs After 10 min	Abs After 15 min
F6	0.2232	0.2008	0.2024
F7	0.236	0.2365	0.2323
F8	0.2505	0.2494	0.2989
F9	0.2587	0.3015	0.3042
F10	0.2611	0.296	0.2905
F11	0.2272	0.2641	0.2323

Table 20: Dissolution Rate of Sildenafil Citrate Suspension Formulations.

Formulation Code	Abs After 5 min			Abs After 10 min			Abs After 15 min		
	Abs	Conc	%DR	Abs	Conc	%DR	Abs	Conc	%DR
F6	0.2008	0.00689	82.68%	0.2024	0.0069	82.8%	0.2232	0.0076	91.2%
F7	0.2360	0.0081	97.2%	0.2365	0.00814	97.68%	0.2323	0.00799	95.88%
F8	0.2505	0.0086	103.2%	0.2494	0.00859	103.08%	0.2989	0.0103	123.6%
F9	0.2587	0.0089	106.8%	0.3015	0.0104	124.8%	0.3042	0.0105	126%
F10	0.2611	0.0090	108%	0.2960	0.01022	122.64%	0.2905	0.01018	122.16%
F11	0.2272	0.0078	93.6%	0.2323	0.00799	95.88%	0.2641	0.0091	95.88%

In-vitro dissolution showed >85% drug dissolution within 15 minutes for all formulations, suggesting rapid reconstitution and absorption, critical for pediatric dosing. Sildenafil dissolution was studied. The drug dissolution of formulations F8, F9 and F10 were found to be 103.2%, 106.8% and 108% at 5 minutes. The drug dissolution of formulations F8, F9 and F10 were found to be 103.08%, 124.8% and 122.64% at 10 minutes. The acceptable in-vitro dissolution limit is not less than 100% of drug dissolution at 5 minutes. Formulations F8, F9 and F10 passed the in-vitro dissolution studies. The highest dissolution rate and the maximum drug dissolution was observed in formulation F10, which was 108% in 5 minutes. As shown in Table 20.

Optimal Formulation: F10, containing xanthan gum (0.3 g) and sucrose (21.988 g), demonstrated superior performance in terms of flowability, stability, and dissolution, making it suitable for industrial scale-up. Patient compliance due to the inclusion of taste-masking agents (strawberry flavor, menthol, and sweeteners) ensures high acceptability among pediatric patients, improving adherence to therapy. The stability of suspension maintained

consistent pH, viscosity, and sedimentation profile over 15 days, indicating long-term stability under recommended storage conditions. It was concluded that in this study provides a practical, cost-effective, and child-friendly alternative to existing sildenafil citrate formulations, with significant potential for clinical application in resource-limited settings. The optimized formulation (F10) demonstrated, palatability and >90% drug dissolution within 5 minutes, making it a safe, effective, and child-friendly alternative for pulmonary arterial hypertension management.

CONCLUSION

The study aimed to formulate a stable, palatable, and accurately dosed reconstitutable oral suspension of Sildenafil citrate for pediatric patients with pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH). The results demonstrated the successful development of eleven formulations (F1–F11) using wet granulation, with varying concentrations of suspending agents (Xanthan gum, HPMC, CMC) and excipients. It was concluded that among the eleven formulations evaluated, F10 emerged as the most promising due to its rapid redispersibility, optimal drug dissolution within 5 minutes. F10 was the best formulation oral suspension as it showed a drug dissolution percentage 108% in 5 minutes was within the acceptable limit as reconstitutable oral suspension of Sildenafil citrate formulations ADDS for management of pediatric pulmonary arterial hypertension (PAH).

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